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Effect of Smartphones as Instructional Tools on Students' Achievement in Agricultural Water Engineering in Colleges of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study used Smartphones as instructional tools to determine their effects on students' achievement in Agricultural Water Engineering in Colleges of Education North-Central, Nigeria. Three purposes of the study were stated, three research questions were posed and answered using means and standard deviations, while three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Quasi-experimental design of non-randomized pre-test post-test control group design was utilized. The research was carried out in four selected Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria, with the population of 16,016 NCE Students in 10 Colleges of Education. 387 NCE III students were sampled from the four selected Colleges of Education in the study area. The research instrument was the Basic Agricultural Water Engineering Achievement Test (BAWEAT). The BAWEAT was validated by three experts. The reliability of the

instruments was 0.71. The results of the study indicated that the students that were taught using smartphones as instructional tools improved in their achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering more than those taught without Smartphones. Recommendations made include use of smartphones as instructional tool should be incorporated among instructional materials for lecture delivery by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) in the curriculum for both teaching and learning activities in the Colleges of Education in North-central among others. Relevant and adequate suggestions such as replicating the work to another area of study and conducting similar study using other courses at the Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Smartphone as Instructional Tools, Basic Agricultural Water Engineering, Academic Achievement, Colleges of Education, Gender

Introduction

Information and communications and technology (ICT) is one of the fastest growing industries in the economic world. It has reduced the high-level of unemployment in economies of many countries including Nigeria. The twenty-first century has been associated with technology utilization, with ICT becoming an essential part of life because of its advanced features which enable people to use their Smartphone to accomplish various daily tasks (Coca & Slisko, 2013). Based on the Global Mobile Association Report (2015), half of the world's population possesses a mobile phone subscription, with Smartphone adoption already reaching critical mass in developed markets. It further explains that smartphones are now responsible for sixty per cent (60%) of internet connections around the world.

Smartphone use its associated technology to advance with simple calls and text messaging, being replaced with functions such as internet access, emails, camera applications and multi-media services. The Apple Company, London in 2007 launched its first-ever Smartphones application simultaneously marking the impact of its achievement on education with its learning mobile application (Apple Press Information, 2013). The report asserts that the possible influence of the mobile device on higher education and their impact on life-long learning opportunities, seem unclear because of technology utilization. Being an evolving area of study, which needed laudable sensitization in every society, this study is aimed at bringing the Smartphone technology to the doorsteps of teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in North-Central Nigeria.

In the educational context, smartphone is an instructional tool which is designed for the development, utilization, management and evaluation of processes as well as resources for learning (Agbetuyi & Oluwatayo, 2012). Instructional usage of smartphones involves a wide range of applications, communication and technologies utilized for information retrieval, research and administration. According to Mtega, Bernard, Msungu and Sanais (2012), the Smartphone as an instructional tool can provide suitable learning platforms as it has a lot of applications which both tutors and learners could use in their academic activities. The authors further explained that Smartphone as instructional tools could be used as an electronic learning tool through mobile computation devices in the classroom settings and government administrative offices.

An instructional tool is any device that has a learning platform which aims to convey learning instructions (Hsu, Ching & Snelson, 2014). Smaldino, Lowthers, Mims and Russell (2014) contended that the purpose of the instructional tool is to facilitate communication and learning for students' achievement. It serves as an educational tool and has a sensor where it uses learning programmes in the classroom and the outside environment, which could be in the framework of communication, interaction of lecturers and students in the learning process. Smartphone is the instructional tool where lecturers in Colleges of Education could use for more advanced applications in teaching and learning for enhanced, achievement in Agricultural Water Engineering in Colleges of Education in North-central, Nigeria.

The content or synopsis of Basic Agricultural Water Engineering (AGE324) as a course, deals with the meaning and importance of water engineering in agriculture; sources of water, soil and water conservation; prevention of soil erosion; irrigation systems; installation and maintenance; classification of soil water table; field investigation for drainage; water drainage and control; types and advantages of drainage systems; problems associated with irrigation and drainage; local harvesting of water for family and community uses; as well as the curriculum of Vocational and Technical Education in Colleges of Education in Nigeria (Enewereuzoh, Igbokwe & Ukegbu, 2017). The course focuses on giving students skills to manage water in the process of carrying out farming activities. The study could consider the Basic Agricultural Water Engineering concepts by using Smartphone as instructional tool to enable lecturers and agricultural education students to have effective teaching and learning activities in the lecture room for enhanced academic achievement of knowledge.

Agricultural education students are those in Colleges of Education who are actively involved in classroom interaction with lecturers on the basic concepts of the Agricultural Water Engineering course through lecture methods and Smartphone as instructional tool in teaching and learning process (National Commission for Colleges of Education, 2014). The students are to be taught the concepts of Agricultural Water Engineering in the curriculum so that they could understand and develop skills in the application and problem-solving that would occur in an agricultural setting (Agbulu & Wever, 2011). In this study, Agricultural Education students are those learners subjected to the study using a Smartphone as instructional tool and those that are not in the classroom environment through a course titled "Basic Agricultural Water Engineering" for enhanced academic achievement.

Wordu and Akor (2018) reported that interest facilitates learning, improves understanding, and stimulates group effort and personal involvement. If a student is interested in a course, one could continue to study even when distracted by other students for enhanced academic achievement.

Ogundokun and Adeyemo (2010) reported that in the school setting, academic achievement is the exhibiting of knowledge attained, or skills developed in school subjects indicated by the test scores or marks assigned by teachers or lecturers after going training in a course for fixed duration. Academic achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering is a reflection of the extent to which the learners have acquired the intended knowledge and skills (Patrick, 2014). Abakpa (2011) asserts that academic achievement is the measure of

accomplishment in a specific field of study. Bacon (2011) reports that academic achievement is standardized test scores and grades of students in the discipline after undergoing training. Hence, academic achievement is the extent to which students, teachers or institutions have achieved their short or long-term educational goals.

Indeed, if students are exposed to learning methods with a good approach such as using a Smartphone as an instructional tool, they could attain high academic achievement (McCoy, 2013). In this present work, academic achievement refers to the measure of knowledge attained, and skills developed by the students in the Basic Agricultural Water Engineering on the stated objectives for the duration of the study irrespective of gender.

Gender is the classification of individuals into male and female, which is determined biologically because of the sexual traits of an individual (Honmane, Iji, Agbo-Egwu & Anyagh, 2020). Gender is a socially ascribed attribute, which differentiates feminine from the masculine (Aniodoh & Egbo, 2013). The authors stressed that gender of learners is a factor that affects students' academic achievement. Over some decades, there has been evidence of bridging the gender gap in educational achievement in many countries. Gender bias seems responsible for the inequality in opportunity, access, enrollment, curriculum, subject disciplines, among others (Gibbs, Fergusson & Harwood, 2012). Thus, reports on academic achievement based on gender are not in synergy. Dalabu (2013) contended that the males performed significantly better than their females' counterpart in assessing the science concept. Eze (2013) maintained that men and women flourish educationally when given the same supportive environment. The author stressed that biological differences of gender are equal in their intellectual abilities, but differences may occur due to social presence and discrimination. Honmane, Takor and Fekumo (2020) in their research indicated that there is significant difference between male and female students in mathematics achievement test.

Afuwaps (2011) reported that the performance of male and female students in basic science had no significant difference in academic achievement. The effects seem to be the change that occurs in the achievement after some treatment. This would be determined by subtracting the mean achievement and retention of the students before the treatment from the mean after the treatment. The value obtained will represent the effect of the treatment on each of the two groups of students (males and females). Therefore, there is the need to examine the effects of Smartphone as instructional tool and lecture method of instruction on students' achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering (AGE324) in Colleges of Education in North-central, Nigeria.

Smartphone users among tertiary level students have increased tremendously in recent years. Higher learning institutions such as Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, Monotechnics and Universities, among others need to determine good strategies to enhance students' Smartphone use to create more inspiring learning environment. The college students mostly use their smartphones for social media interaction and seem not to be exploring its maximum utilization in the academic environment. It has been observed that a good proportion of Agricultural Education students in different Colleges of Education in Nigeria usually experience very low performance in Agricultural Water Engineering (AGE324) course in their Nigeria Certification in Education III programme. Perhaps this

could be due to a number of factors such as ineffective instructional strategies adopted by lecturers, lack of innovative instructional devices and tools, low interest of the students, low perception of some important basic concepts, which are not comprehended by male and female NCE III students, inability to retain the concepts taught after a while, due to inadequate instructional tool, inappropriate use and application of teaching methods.

The present study, therefore, could attempt to proffer solutions to these questions to determine the effect of smart phones as instructional tool on agricultural education students' achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering in College of Education in North-central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- i. What are the mean achievement scores of NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with Smartphone as instructional tool in and those taught without Smartphone as instructional tool?
- ii. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering concepts with smartphone as instructional tool?
- iii. What is the interaction effect of Smartphone as instructional tool on males and females NCE III students' mean achievement scores in Agricultural Water Engineering?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with Smartphone as instructional tool in and those taught without Smartphone as instructional tool.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with smartphone as instructional tool.
- iii. There is no significant interaction effect of Smartphone as instructional tool on males and females NCE III students' mean achievement scores in Agricultural Water Engineering.

Methodology

The research adopted the pre-test post-test non-randomized design. The target population of the study comprises 16,016 NCE III students in Agricultural Water Engineering in North Central Nigeria. 387 students were randomly selected from four Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria for the study.

The instrument for the study was Basic Agricultural Water Engineering Achievement Test (BAWEAT) and treatment material is Smartphone as Instructional Tool (SIT). BAWEAT is made up of 32 multiple choice objective questions from Agricultural Water Engineering. The instrument was validated by three experts, one in Mathematics Education,

one in Educational Foundation and General Studies, and one in Biology Education, all from Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi (JOSTUM), Nigeria.

All the experimental groups were given the Pre-test before the treatment and after treatment post-tests were administered on them. The experimental group one was exposed to the use of Smartphone as instructional Tool in teaching the Agricultural Water Engineering concepts while the control group was taught without smartphone. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean achievement scores of NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with Smartphone as instructional tool in and those taught without Smartphone as instructional tool?

The answer to this research question is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement Scores of NCE III Students taught Agricultural Water Engineering Concepts with Smartphone and those taught with Conventional Method

Group	N	Pre-	SD	Post-	SD	Mean Gain
		BAWEAT Mean		BAWEAT Mean		
Experimental Group	122	7.75	2.20	16.09	3.45	8.34
Control Group	265	6.69	2.30	14.05	4.37	7.36
Mean difference		1.06		2.04		0.99
Total	387					

Table 1 shows that at pre-test, the experimental group had a mean score of 7.75 with a standard deviation of 2.20, while the control group had a mean score of 6.69 with a standard deviation of 2.30. Their mean difference was 1.06. At post-test, the experimental group had a mean score of 16.09 with a standard deviation of 3.45 while the control group had a mean score of 14.05 with a standard deviation of 4.37. Their mean difference was 2.04. The mean gain was 0.99 in favour of the experimental group.

Research Question Two

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering concepts with smartphone as instructional tool?

The answer to this research question is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement Scores of Male and Female NCE III Students taught Agricultural Water Engineering Concepts with Smartphone

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post- test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	80	8.98	2.45	22.29	4.98	13.51
Female	42	8.78	2.24	16.85	3.69	8.07
Mean difference		0.20		5.44		5.44
Total	122					

Table 2 shows that at pre-test, male students had a mean score of 8.98 with a standard deviation of 2.45 while the female students had a mean score of 8.78 with a standard deviation of 2.24. Their mean difference was 0.20. At post-test, male students had a mean score of 22.29 with a standard deviation of 4.98 while the female students had a mean score of 16.85 with a standard deviation of 3.69. Their mean difference was 5.44 and mean gain was 5.44 in favour of male students.

Research Question Three

What is the interaction effect of Smartphone as instructional tool on males and females NCE III students' mean achievement scores in Agricultural Water Engineering?

Answer to this research question is presented in Table 3

Table 3: The Interaction Effect of SIT on Male and Female on NCE III Students' Mean Achievement Scores in Agricultural Water Engineering

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	17042.04 ^a	2	8521.02	955.443	.044	.087
Intercept	5011.90	1	5011.90	581.973	.003	.529
Pre-test Achieve	17042.04	1	17042.04	1910.778	.070	.049
Groups	667.352	1	667.352	74.929	.040	.128
Groups*Gender	203.433	1	203.433	22.810	.045	.083
Error	3406.820	382	8.9184			
Total	48240.000	387				
Corrected Total	3369.820	386				

a: R. Squared = .087 (Adjusted R Squared = .064)

The interaction effect of smartphone as instructional tool (SIT) on male and female NCE III students' mean achievement scores is read from Table 3 across the row heading Groups*Gender and column headings Partial Eta. Groups*Gender: Partial Eta Square = .087, $p = 0.045$, at $df = 1$. The calculated percentage of interaction effect of SIT on male and female NCE III students' mean achievement scores as obtained from the Adjusted R

Squared ($.064 \times 100 = 6.4\%$) is 6.4%. This result indicates that there was an interaction effect.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with Smartphone as instructional tool in and those taught without Smartphone as instructional tool.

The test of this hypothesis is presented in Table 4

Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Achievement Scores of NCE III Students in Agricultural Water Engineering Taught with Smartphone and Those taught without Smartphone as Instructional Tool (SIT)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	10979.987 ^a	2	5489.994	315.372	.001	.068
Intercept	87.680	1	87.680	5.0367	.034	.028
Pre-test Achievement	6987.454	1	6987.454	400.813	.001	.058
Groups	667.352	1	667.352	38.336	.030	.128
Error	6649.968	382	17.408			
Total	48240.000	387				
Corrected Total	3369.820	386				

a: R. Squared = .068 (Adjusted R Squared = .047)

Table 4 shows that p-value of 0.03 was less than the significant level of 0.05. Since the p-value of 0.03 was less than the significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected. This means that there was a significant difference in the mean interest rating of NCE III students taught Agricultural water engineering concepts with SIT and those taught without Smartphones.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female NCE III students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with smartphone as instructional tool.

The result of this hypothesis is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ANCOVA Result of Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female NCE III Students Taught Agricultural Water Engineering with Smartphone as Instructional Tool

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	168.874 ^a	2	84.437	2.094	.051	.067
Intercept	2543.349	1	1543.349	38.280	.001	.428
Pre-test Achievement	7.750	1	7.750	0.1930	.518	.015
Groups	730.897	1	730.897	18.128	.001	.123
Groups*Gender	1.461	1	1.461	0.0362	.001	.045
Error	4838.097	120	40.317			
Total	69873.009	122				
Corrected Total	6467.978	121				

a: R. Squared = .413 (Adjusted R Squared = .410)

Table 5 shows that p-value of 0.001 was less than the significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value of 0.001 was less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mean interest ratings in learning of Agricultural water engineering concepts of the students who were taught with and those taught without smartphone as instructional tool (SIT).

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant interaction effect of Smartphone as instructional tool on males and females NCE III students' mean achievement scores in Agricultural Water Engineering.

The result of this hypothesis is presented in Table 6

Table 6: ANCOVA Result of Interaction Effect of with Smartphone on Male and Female NCE III Students Mean Achievement Scores in Agricultural Water Engineering

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3240.309 ^a	2	1620.15	34.781	.000	.412
Intercept	134.628	1	134.628	2.890	.120	.028
Pre-Interest	3154.584	1	3154.584	67.721	.000	.424
Groups	5174.489	1	5174.489	111.083	.000	.447
Groups*Gender	137.948	1	137.948	2.961	1.243	.027
Error	5589.87	120	46.582			
Total	1600089.04	122				
Corrected Total	66848.24	121				

a. R. Squared = .048 (Adjusted R Squared = .025)

Table 6 shows that the p-value of 0.052 was greater than the significant level of 0.05. Since the p-value of 0.052 was greater than the significant level of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference was not rejected. This means that there was no significant interaction effect of Smartphone on male and female NCE III students mean achievement scores in learning Agricultural Water Engineering concepts. Also, the Smartphone interaction effect size on male and female NCE III students' achievement scores in Agricultural Water Engineering concepts was small (0.03).

Discussion

The NCE III Students taught Agricultural Water Engineering concepts with Smartphone as instructional tools have enhanced academic achievement. This outcome agrees with Wordu and Akor (2018) who found out that the usage of the mobile devices helped students to solve academic problems and also got their information via visual tools like television, computers and internet. Therefore, study materials that are related to what students are used to such as mobile devices, video games, television which captured the students' attention and cooperation made teaching and learning a joyous experience. The results of the study indicate a paradigm shift in favour of efficient inclusion of emergent technologies in instructional processes, particularly at the tertiary education level (Anyor & Abah, 2014).

The findings also revealed that students taught Agricultural Water Engineering with smartphones improved in their interest during the period of study more than those taught without smartphone. This is similar Adjei (2019) who also found that students who were taught using iPads, computer based instructional techniques, computer assisted instruction, multimedia instruction and computer-based instruction achieved higher than those taught with conventional methods. The reason for the better achievement of students taught with smartphones as an instructional tool may most likely be that students taught with smartphone had the opportunity of interacting with both real and simulated material, whereas students taught without smartphone as an instructional tool did not interact with the smartphone which gave students taught with smartphone better opportunity to form their own cognitive models. Using smartphone devices to learn Agricultural Water Engineering concepts provide students with access to multiple representations of phenomena and the opportunities to manipulate the device to learn the Agricultural Water Engineering concepts. The findings also showed that the adoption of Smartphone in the Agricultural Water Engineering classroom enhanced NCE III male and female students' achievement. Again, the findings revealed that both sexes improved in their achievement in Agricultural Water Engineering concepts. Though the male improved more than female counterparts, the difference was statistically insignificant. Niga, Hassan, Nor and Malek (2017) found no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students, using Bridge IT mobile application. This implies that if male and female students are given equal opportunities in the learning process using innovative teaching strategies such as smartphone as instructional tool, the educational inequality in our educational system in the terms of gender differences especially in Agricultural Water Engineering may be addressed. Hannelore, Tammy and Tania (2016) maintained that using iPod touch devices and smartphone tools, students in the experimental group did have higher significant mean achievement scores compared to students in the control group.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it could be concluded that smartphones as instructional tools enhanced students' achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering (AGE324) irrespective of the gender. This implies that if AGE324 lecturers use innovative instructional tools such as smartphones, which were found to have enhanced students' achievement, the issue of low achievement in Basic Agricultural Water Engineering by NCE III students at the Colleges of Education level may become a thing of the past. Similarly, the existing gender gap in achievement would also be bridged using smartphones as instructional tools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. There should be constant strong Wi-Fi connections power.
- ii. College administrators should orient students on how effectively they can utilize smartphones for their academic activities.
- iii. Tablet should incorporate among instructional materials for teaching and learning of Basic Agricultural Water Engineering course in Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
- iv. The National Commission for Colleges of Education in corroboration with College administrators supervises the implementation of tablets as instructional tools in the scheme of lesson delivery in their colleges.

REFERENCES

- Abakpa, B.O. (2011). Effects of mastery learning approach on Senior Secondary School Students' achievement: The moderating influence of age intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *The African Symposium; An online Journal of the African Educational Research Network*, 10(2), 127- 141
- Adeyemo, S. A. (2010). The Impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) On Teaching and Learning of Physics. *International Journal of Educational Research and Technology*, 1 (2); 48 – 59.
- Adjei, D. N. (2019). The Use and Effect of Smartphones in Students' Learning Activities: Evidence from the University Of Ghana, Legon. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 2851
- Afuwape, M.O. (2011). Students' Self-concepts and their achievement in Basic Science in Senior Secondary School in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Multidisciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*. 5(4), 191-200.
- Agbetuyi, P.A., & Oluwatayo, J.A. (2012). Information and Communication Technology in Nigeria. *Functional Education Meditarrian Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(3). 41-45.
- Agbulu, N.O., & Wever, D.G. (2011). Introduction to agricultural education.
- Anyor, J. W., & Abah, J. A. (2014). Students' perception of mobile learning in a blended collaborative learning framework in mathematics. *Benue Journal of Mathematics and Mathematics Education*, 1(3), 20-27.
- Apple Press Information (2013). Apple Updates Processors and Prices of Mac Book Pro with Retina Display: PRESS RELEASE February 13, 2013.
- Apple company London (2007). Computer and computing technologies in agricultural. 10th edition' London.

- Atkinson, R.C., & Shiffrin, R. M. (1968). *Human memory. "Proposed system and its control process"* *The psychology of learning and motivation*. New York; Academic Press.
- Bacon, w. (2011). Factors affecting students' quality of academic performance: A case of secondary school level Students. *Journal of Quality and Technology Management*.7(1); 14-21
- Chikendu, R.E., &Okoli, J.N. (2020). Effects of instructional computer animation on secondary school students' achievement in Chemistry in Awka Education Zone. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*7(3); 28-32.
- Coca, D.M., &Slisko, J. (2013). Software socrative and smartphone as a tool for implementation of basic process of active physic learning in classroom: An initiative feasibility study with prospective Teachers: *European Journal of Physics Learning Education*, 4(2), 40-52.
- Dalabu, N.E. (2013). Effects of demonstration method of teaching on Students' achievement in agricultural Science. *World Journal of*
- Enwereuzoh, N.M., Igbokwe, N.C., &Ukegbu, M.N. (2017). The role of National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) in quality Teacher Education for value re-orientation and national development in Nigeria. 10(1),294-306.
- Eze, S.O. (2013). *Fundamentals of research methods and statistics*, Makurdi: Selfers Academic Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Commission for Colleges of Education Minimum Standard for NCE Teachers for Vocational and Technological Education: 6th Edition*. 17-18.
- Hannelore, M. Tammy,C., Joure, V.L., & Tania, M. (2016). Introduction tablet devices during mathematics education: 'is it really a magical learning tool? *International Scientific Research Journal*, 72(7), 393-410
- Honmane, O., Iji, C. O., Agbo-Egwu, A. O. & Anyagh, P. I. (2020). Capturing Secondary School Students' Interest via the Utilization of the Tablet Teaching Strategy in Geometry in Osun State, Nigeria; *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology (IJMTT)*; 66 (1)
- Honmane, O., Takor, D.I. &Fekumo, B. (2020). Effectiveness of the Use of Tablet teaching strategy on Secondary School Students' achievement in Mathematics in Osun State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Invention*; 8(1); 01-06.
- Hsu, Y.C., Ching, Y.H., &Snelson, C. (2014). Research priority in mobile learning: an international delphi study. *Canadian Journal of Learning Technology*. 4(92); 21-230.
- McCoy, B. (2013). Digital Distractions the Classroom: Students Classroom use of Digital Devices for non-classroom related purposes. *Journal of nced Learning* 1(2); 91-110.
- Mtega, W.P., Bernard, R., Msungu, A.C., & Sanare, R. (2012). Using mobile phones for teaching and learning purposes in higher learning institutions: the case study of the Sokoine University of Agriculture in Tanzania. *Proceedings and report of the 5th Ubuntu-Net Alliance Annual Conference* 6(7); 118-129.
- National Commission for Colleges of Education (2014). *National Commission for Colleges of Education: Ranking of Colleges of Education and Other NCE Awarding*

Institutions According to Performance of Their Academic Programmes in the 1999 and 2000.

- Ogundokun, M.O. & Adeyemo, D.A. (2010). Emotional Intelligence and Academic Achievement: the moderating influence of age intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. *The African Journal of Symposium: An Online Journal of Educational Research Network*. 10(2), 127-141.
- Patrick, N.B. (2016). Effect of co-operative learning approach on Secondary School Students academic achievement in Agriculture in Kenya. *International Journal of Human Social and Science Education*.1 (1), 191-197.
- Smaldino, S., Lowthers, D.L.; Mims, C. & Russell, A. (2014). Instructional technology and media for learning. 11th edition: New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- Wordu, H. & Akor, V. O. (2018). Instructional delivery models and academic performance of Agricultural Science Students in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of education and evaluation* 4(9), 77-89.